

Synthesis of N-Methylamino Acids through 1-Methyl-2,5-Disubstituted Imidazolin-4-Ones

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Unsaturated 1-Methyl-2,5-disubstituted imidazolin-4-ones have been prepared by the condensation of suitable aldehydes with a mixture of sarcosine and benzimidic acid esters as well as their hydrochlorides. These imidazolones have been selectively hydrogenated and hydrolysed to N-methylamino acids.

FOLLOWING Kidwai and Deyasia's method¹, 1-Methyl-2,5-disubstituted imidazolin-4-ones (I) have been used as intermediates in the synthesis of N-methylamino acids (III). Methylation of 2,4-disubstituted imidazolin-5-ones leads to methylation on the nitrogen adjacent to the carbonyl group².

Treatment of 2-Phenyl-4-benzylidene imidazolin-5-ones with $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SO}_4/\text{NaOCH}_3$ gave 1-Methyl-2-phenyl-4-benzylidene-imidazolin-5-ones identical with the compound obtained by cyclization of N-methylamide of N-benzoylaminocinnamic acid^{3a,3b}. 1-Methyl-2,5-disubstituted imidazolin-4-ones (I) were, therefore,

TABLE I

R	R'	Method of synthesis	Solvent	M.p. °C	Yield %	Calcd., %			Catalyst	M.p. °C	Yield %	M.p. °C	Yield %	Calcd. %		
						C	H	N						C	H	N
C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	A	W	210	30	77.84	5.38	10.68	Z	—	—	250	45.0	67.00	7.30	7.80
		B			25	77.80	5.25	10.60	Y	—	—			—	66.89	7.25
4HO-C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	A	W	255	60	73.36	5.07	10.07	Y	180	66.3	—	—	—	—	—
		B			40	73.68	5.17	10.23								
4H ₃ CO-C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	A	X	210	55	73.95	5.52	9.58	Z	145	69.3	225	57.7	63.14	7.23	6.69
		B			30	74.01	5.73	9.23	Y					—	—	—
3',4'(H ₃ CO) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	CH ₃	A	X	192	72	70.79	5.63	8.69	Z	—	—	230	16.6	—	—	'b'
		B			45	70.68	5.69	8.96								
3',4',5'(H ₃ CO) ₃ C ₆ H ₂	CH ₃	A	W	193	76	68.17	5.72	7.95	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
		B			45.5	68.26	6.04	7.81								
3',4',5'(H ₃ CO) ₃ C ₆ H ₂	H	A	W	270 (dec.)	82.3	67.44	5.36	8.28	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
					76.8	67.27	5.42	8.01								

A = free esters, B = hydrochlorides, Z = PtO₂, Y = Pd/C(10%), X = EtOAc, W = EtOH.
^a = analysis calcd. for C₁₈H₁₈O₂N₂: C, 73.45; H, 6.16; N, 9.5. found: C, 73.20; H, 6.50; N, 9.38.
^b = analysis for *p*-tosyl derivative, m.p. 162° calcd. for C₁₉H₂₃NO₆S: C, 58.01; H, 5.85; N, 3.56. found: C, 58.06; H, 5.84; N, 3.54.

prepared directly by condensing suitable aldehydes with a mixture of sarcosine and benzimidic acid esters or their hydrochlorides. The introduction of methyl group with its inductive and possibly steric effect seems to lower the reactivity of the methylene group, resulting in lower yields of 1-methyl-2-phenyl-5-arylidene imidazolin-4-ones. The $-N=C<$ bond is also not in a position to affect the reactivity of the methylene group. In view of this, the ratio of the sarcosine ester, benzimidic acid ester and the aldehyde were changed to 1.75 : 1.4 : 1 in the case of free ester and 2.15 : 1 in the case of their hydrochlorides (Cf 1).

1-Methyl-2,5-disubstituted imidazolin-4-Ones (I) are yellow crystalline compounds with sharp melting points. They are quite stable and do not undergo any appreciable oxidation. They give blue to dark violet colour with ethanolic potassium-hydroxide and also reduce ammoniacal silver nitrate. 1-Methyl-2-phenyl-5-benzylidene-imidazolin-4-One gives a 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone.

The exocyclic double bond in 1-Methyl-2-phenyl-5-arylidene imidazolin-4-one was selectively reduced using both PtO_2 and 10% Pd/C ^{1,2a,3c} The N-methyl imidazolones took longer to undergo hydrogenation. The saturated 5-aryl compounds (II), were difficult to isolate. They were unaffected by 1% aqueous or ethanolic NaOH . Barium hydroxide (40%) and also NaOH (20%) directly hydrolysed these saturated imidazolones to N-methyl amino acids. Under these conditions it was not possible to isolate either the N-methylacylamino acids or their amides. Table I summarises the synthetic work.

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